

A Discourse Analysis of Norminalization in IGBO Language

Ngozi L Dom-Anyanwu

College of Languages and Communication Arts Education

Lagos State University of Education, Ijanikin, Lagos State

Corresponding Author: Ngozi L Dom-Anyanwu ngozidom@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Discourse, Analysis, Norminalization, Discourse Analysis

Received : 23, July

Revised : 24, August

Accepted: 25, September

©2023 Dom-Anyanwu: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This paper looks at how Igbo people use their language in general interactions. Discourse analysis of Igbo norminalization therefore looks at what and how the Igbo norminals are realize in their interactions both in written and oral forms. The main objective of this study is to indicate and expose the impacts of normalization as well as show how nouns are derived from other word classes in Igbo language. The method used in this study is discourse analysis method which is used to analyze connected speech or writing of the Igbo. Primary and secondary sources are used for data gathering. The study adopts the structural grammar theoretical framework prominently used by Bloomfield in 1914. The paper looks at the processes of forming Igbo nouns from other word classes. The study concludes that norminalization exists in Igbo language discourse and it is derived from word classes like, norminals, noun phrase, verb phrase and even sentences. And this makes Igbo language oral and written form perfect in every discourse.

INTRODUCTION

“Discourse Analysis is for me, more than just language use. It is a language use seen in its oral or written form. In the views of Mey (2001), Discourse is seen as the “Universe” of language use, the sum total of what people do with each other in interaction. Therefore, Discourse Analysis can be seen as a study of human language in written and spoken form in a social situation. It’s aim is to study how human language is used in its real/natural form in a given society or social situation.

It does not focus only on the use of language but also on the contextual meaning of language. This simply means that discourse analysis lay emphasis on the spoken and written aspects of language in a real life communication situation. That is, the way people use language in a social situation to achieve whatever they want to achieve. It can be in a conflict situation, emotional situation, religious situation and even traditional situation.

Discourse Analysis is credited to Zellig Harris, a linguist who saw it as a method of analysis connected speech or writing, a method for communicating linguistic description beyond the limits of a single sentence at a time and a means of correlating culture and language (Ezeifeka, 2018).

The key element in discourse is the effort to interpret and how we can accomplish it.

On the other hand, nominalization is a word formation in which some parts of speech are transformed and used as a noun in a communicative and social situation.

It can also be seen as a way or process of forming nouns from other classes of words. In the words of Halliday (2004), “normalization refers to the phenomenon that any element or group of elements, phrase or clause can function as nominal structure”. Lei et al (2019), see nominalization as a creative formation process through which words of all parts of speech could be converted into nouns.

According to Nwagboo (2021) quoting Tallerman (2005), normalization is making something into a noun and specifically the process of turning a verb into a noun. In this process, the noun in addition to the modifier it has, occurs in a typical noun phrase position such as subject position or object position in the sentence. The nouns and nominals have a wide variety of morphological and structural slopes with elements from other functional categories. And that is exactly how it works in Igbo language discourse. Nominalization according to Crystal (2008), is the process of forming a noun from some other word classes. Example, dark + ness = darkness.

An affix which is used to derive a noun from a verb is called nominalizer. Affixation and reduplication are some of the most common and most productive and prolific processes for nominalization in Igbo language.

The Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is:

- to indicate and expose the impacts of nominalization on Igbo discourse.
- to identify the categories of nominalization in Igbo oral and written language as well as to show how the nouns are derived from other word classes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study adopts the structural grammar – theoretical framework. Prominent scholar of this theory was Bloomfield who in (1914) regarded normalization as endocentric construction and put forward a method of classifying words, which is “immediate constitute analysis”. For Bloomfield, normalization can be formed by the combination of derivative word or subordinate endocentric construction adding head, but it all belongs to noun. The centre of this structural theory is form and not meaning or function.

METHODOLOGY

The method used in this study is oral discourse analysis method and discussion from some Igbo indigenes. This was done particularly to know how they derive nouns in Igbo language.

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Categories of Normalization in Igbo Language

Categories of normalization in Igbo language has to do with the derivation of noun from other word classes thus; deriving noun from phrases, deriving noun from nominal phrases, deriving noun from verb phrases, deriving noun from sentence.

(1) Deriving Noun from Norminals:

This can be done by main root reduplication in combination with interfixation or by reduplication alone. For examples:

- | | | | |
|-------|------------------------|---|-------------|
| (i) | ɔwa + ta + ɔwa | = | ɔwataɔwa |
| | world interfix world | = | Eternity |
| (ii) | Anɔ + m + Anɔ | = | Anɔmanɔ |
| | Animal interfix Animal | = | Animal |
| (iii) | Ogo + l + Ogo | = | Ogologo |
| | high + interfix + high | = | length |
| (iv) | Nka + Nka | = | Nkanka |
| | Old + old | = | Hargard |
| (v) | Nna + Nna | = | Nnanna |
| | Father + Father | = | Grandfather |
| (vi) | Ike + Ike | = | Ikike |
| | Strength Strength | = | Authority |

Looking at the above examples, the first 3 examples of noun are derived from reduplication and interfixation.

Examples (iv) and (v) are derived from reduplication above and example (vi) is derived from partial reduplication. In all, all the nouns above are derived from norminals in Igbo Discourse.

(2) Deriving Nouns from Noun Phrase

There are norminals that are derived from noun phrases. This is common among Igbo personal names. These can mainly be seen among noun, noun constructions. Though there are few of them that

can be seen in form of noun, adjective constructions. Examples of noun - noun construction (N1+N2) include:

- (i) Ada + Eze = Adaeze
Daughter + King = Daughter of the king
- (ii) Obi + Oha = Obioha
Heart + people = People's mind
- (iii) Okoro + ocha = Okoroocha
Youth + white = Fair in complexion youth
- (iv) Àgbò, + ínmā = Agbomma
Specie + beauty = Specie of beautiful people

Looking at the above examples (i) and (ii) are derived from noun, noun construction (N1 + N2). While the N1 is the head of the NP, N2 is the modifier. The (iii) and (iv) examples are sequence of noun and adjectives. While the N1 is the head, the adjective modifies the noun. On the other hand, non-personal names can also be derived from noun phrase in Igbo norminalization process. For examples:

- Ulo + Aku = Uloaku
House + Wealth = Bank
- Oba + Ji = Obaji
barn + yam = Yam barn
- Ulo + Akwukwo = Uloakwukwo
House + School = School
- Aka + oru = Akaoru
Hand + work = Profession
- Ulo + ogwu = Uloogwu
House + medicine = Hospital
- Oba + Ede = Obaede
barn + cocoyam = Cocoyam barn
- Ulo + Ego = Uloego
House + money = Bank

(3) Deriving Nouns from Verb Phrase

There are various Igbo norminals that can be derived from verb phrases, thus:

(i) Harmonizing verbal prefix and infix and inherent complement of the verb to the verb root. For example:

- E + zu + m + ike = Ezumike
Pre/verb/infix/complement = Holiday
- E + bu + m + onu = Ebumonu
Pre/verb/infix/complement = Fasting
- A + zu + m + Ahia = Azumahia
Pre/verb/infix/complement = Trading
- E + kpe + m + ekpe = Ekpemekpe
Pre/verb/infix/complement = Praying

Norminals can also be derived from the verb phrases through the attachment of homogenic syllabic nasal prefixes to the verb-root and their inherent complement. Good examples include:

- M + bu + aja = Mbuaja
snp/ vr/ complement = Tipper
- M + gba + ama = Mgbaama
snp/ vr/ complement = Sign bearer
- M + tọ + ọchi = Mtọọchi
snp/ vr/ complement = Comedy
- N + Ja + ike = Njaike
snp/ vr/ complement = Promoter

(4) Deriving Nouns from Sentences

Some Igbo norminals are derived from sentences. This is common among the Igbo personal names. In the words of Ogbonna (2009), the Igbo sentential personal names exhibit such varieties in structure and in function that one may think all Igbo sentences are possibly utilized for Igbo personal names. The Igbo sentential names appear in different moods thus:

- Declarative = Chi + nwe + ndu Chinwendu
- Interrogative = Onye + ka + chi Onyekachi
- Imperative = Che + ta + chi Chetachi
- Explanatory = Chukwu + Emeka Chukwuemeka

Looking at normalization in Igbo language, one can see clearly and conclude that norminalization is derived from noun, verb, norminals and even sentences in Igbo oral and written discourse. Therefore, discourse analysis plays a very important role in Igbo normalization. And norminalization has a very important position in Igbo language as far as oral and written communications are concerned.

The results of the study included:

- the derivation of Igbo nouns from nominals, noun
- the derivation of phrase, verb phrase and sentence phrase. These were gathered from the owners of the language through oral discourse.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study looked into the discourse analysis of norminalization in Igbo languages. The paper looked at the process of forming Igbo nouns from other word classes. This study concluded that norminalization exists in Igbo language discourse and it is derived from word classes like: noun phrase, verb phrase, norminals and sentence phrase.

For the effective learning of all the aspects of Igbo language, discourse in both oral and written aspect of the language is very important. Therefore, the Igbo language teachers must always create avenues for the learners to visit the owners of the language and hear from them on certain issues concerning the

general discourse in Igbo language. This will help them know how some words are derived from others.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

The researcher suggest that further studies should be carried out on other aspects of Igbo language such as negative, and more studies on norminalization.

REFERENCES

- Bloomfield, L. (1914). *An Introduction to the Study of Language*. London: Bell and Sons.
- Crystal, Dr. (2008). *A Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics*. (6th Ed). Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
- Ezeifeka, C. R. (2018). *Discourse analysis: Concepts and Approaches*. Awka: Patrobas.
- Halliday, M.A.K. (2004). *An Introduction to Functional Grammar*. Bei Jing: Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press.
- Lei, Y. and Yi, Z. (2019). "An Analysis of Research on Norminalization by Major Linguistics Schools". *International Journal of Liberal Arts and Social Sciences*, 7(4) 15-25.
- Mey, L. (2001). *Pragmatics An Introduction*. Beijing: Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press.
- Nwagboo, G. O. (2021). *Lecture Note on Norminalization*. Faculty of Art UNILAG.